

OPINION ARTICLE

Linking registries to deliver standardised NCD indicators in the European Health Data Space: why do we need a Collaborative Health Information European Framework (CHIEF)

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Introduction

The availability of actionable information is critical to plan and implement effective strategies for health improvement. Today, the correct governance of health systems requires interpretable models and timely indicators on population needs, quality of care and health outcomes (1).

Despite the increasing availability of health-related data, the capacity of institutions and healthcare organisations to monitor their performance using the available databases, particularly in the area of non-communicable diseases (NCDs), is still hampered by structural factors (2). The implementation of recent EU regulations such as GDPR (3), the Data Act (4) and the Data Governance Act (5) also have an impact on the ease of linking data between different entities.

A joint project carried out by the European Commission (EC) and the World Health Organization (WHO), found that heterogeneous information systems co-exist across Europe, ranging not only in design (from population-based registries to service-oriented databases), but also in information sources (electronic health records, EHRs, to multiple linked datasets) with a varying degree of flexibility, data quality and sustainability. The report concluded that “the sharing of experiences among neighbouring countries or regions may become an important catalyser” (3).

Other key aspects include the heterogeneous information infrastructure at national and sub-national level and relevant methodological challenges arising in the measurement of complex indicators, e.g. multimorbidity and heterogeneous data quality. Furthermore, information on different diseases remains fragmented across different silos and contexts (3).

To overcome these problems, a holistic approach would seem most appropriate to tackle the diverse operating conditions through which data are processed in different social, political and cultural contexts of European countries (6,7).

The goal of integrating efforts from different disease areas and multiple disciplines suggests new forms of collaboration to build platforms for the continuous production of indicators across the European Union (EU), which will remain a need beyond the aims of the European Health Data Space - EHDS (8) to facilitate access to data.

In 2022, the European Commission started the “Healthier together” programme with the aim of identifying and implementing effective policies and actions to reduce the burden of major NCDs (9).

The five-year initiative is expected to roll out a stream of activities to enhance the response of health systems to a range of conditions, including health determinants, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, chronic respiratory diseases, mental health and neurological disorders. The different areas of NCDs involve similar information challenges that would be extremely convenient to tackle under a common overarching approach.

In support of this programme, the Commission’s Directorate-General of Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE) and the Joint Research Centre (JRC) launched an initiative to deliver the essential elements of a common EU indicator framework that could be applied seamlessly across major NCDs. The “Collaborative Health Information European Framework” (CHIEF) is an EU think-tank of new ideas and solutions, specifically designed to overcome the difficulties and hindrances towards the regular collection of NCD indicators experienced by recent EU projects.

The scope of CHIEF is “to provide expert input in the form of concepts and solutions for the design and implementation of a sustainable information system that will enable the periodic collection and progressive scalability of an EU-harmonised set of indicators across NCDs, within the current and future flagship initiatives”.

Although focusing on the indicator-collection process, the aim of CHIEF is to tackle the broader perspectives of the interoperability of systems and the advanced statistical and epidemiological approaches needed to assess and integrate the study of comorbidity into the analysis of NCDs.

The initiative has the merit to consider expectations of the public as an integral part of the plan, establishing the necessary interrelations across fundamental flagship programmes such as the joint action on cardiovascular diseases and diabetes (10) and the European health data space - EHDS (11).

Important issues concerning data quality, metadata representation, the application of valid statistical methods and data cleaning/harmonisation are also considered as part of the CHIEF initiative.

Structure of the collaboration

To expedite the realisation of its goals, the initiative has been conceived as an agile forum, through which experts can collaborate within and across disease groups, towards the finalisation of activities that will be run through a mix of remote and in-person work, teleconferences and annual meetings.

The work of experts has been coordinated through the formation of multidisciplinary “design working groups”, each tackling the separate challenges involved within three different points of focus:

- **“Metadata”**, to define the type and contents of the documentation required to integrate the different data sources available for the continuous production of NCD indicators across different disease domains. This point of focus includes challenges regarding the information infrastructure, including *common data elements* (CDEs) with specific attention for risk factors across NCDs, *evaluation methods* (reliability of data sources for the calculation of indicators, data quality score and capture-recapture methods) and *target indicators* (epidemiology, prevention, diagnosis, treatment and outcomes). In this context, a key interest is the FAIR-ification of data elements used for the production of indicators.
- **“Federated data analysis”**, showcasing relevant analytical solutions that can help the EU and Member States (MS) to report on NCDs effectively, resolving the major methodological challenges of sharing information from the existing data sources, without sharing personal data. This point of focus addresses a series of methodological challenges, including those in relation to performing a longitudinal analysis of federated databases using specific parameters (e.g. time to diagnosis), and how to process heterogeneous databases avoiding bias and misinterpretation (12).
- **“Barriers and enablers towards implementation”**, understanding the barriers hampering the implementation of regulations, with the direct participation of relevant stakeholders. This point of focus addresses challenges regarding the social barriers to the implementation of NCD information systems, including the effects of current EU regulations and the role of stakeholders such as decision makers, health professionals and people with NCDs. The specific angle of the latter set of stakeholders involves the direct participation of citizens in the calculation of indicators. This has been a neglected aspect up until now and will be redressed within CHIEF.

CHIEF has taken diabetes as its starting point due to the inroads already made in a stream of projects carried out by the EUBIROD network (13), through its identification of the key elements of the points of focus specified above for the progressive expansion towards additional disease domains (14-18).

Expected results

The results obtained for all points of focus will help define the foundations of a common health information system that can act as a model for the continuous monitoring of NCDs. In particular, the direct participation of citizens has been acknowledged as a driving force to deliver a high-quality core set of indicators that matter to people with NCDs.

The outputs of CHIEF can be used as the building blocks of a modern form of learning health system (LHS) that can accelerate the uptake of indicators using data and digitalisation to connect clinicians and patients for the common goal of sustainable health improvement (19).

For each focus, CHIEF takes into full consideration the “pillars” represented by the set of social, scientific, technological and cultural aspects at the basis of EU policies and regulations (such as the GDPR, EHDS, Data Act, Data Governance Act, etc.).

The initial set of papers included in the present issue of *Frontiers* are extracted from the first series of reports delivered during the last two years by the diabetes design working group (“CHIEF-diabetes.dwg”), building upon the expertise of the EUBIROD network.

In each technical report, the expert group has addressed the evolution of activities and regulations that are key to support the implementation of health indicators. Each report includes recommendations for the calculation of a list of core indicators in diabetes, used as a basis for the implementation of a platform specifically designed to produce NCD indicators on a rolling basis.

The framework considers the current systems of data collection (applied by institutions such as EUROSTAT, OECD, WHO, International Diabetes Federation – IDF, and global standards applicable by data sources and registers networks such as the International Consortium for Health Outcomes Measurement - ICHOM).

The recommendations delivered by each point of focus are consistent with the theory of LHS on three different levels:

- “practice to data”, i.e. how the data are collected in real life situations: a) Indicator framework, diabetes indicators core set; b) Metadata: definition, semantic description, and FAIR-ification;
- “data to knowledge”, i.e. how data is analysed to understand phenomena: a) Operational plan to build a coherent EU information system for NCDs: design of targeted studies for the timely reporting of NCD indicators in EHDS; b) A proposal for a federated data analysis framework with practical examples provided of specific indicators; c) Updated method to carry out automated reviews of data sources and registers across NCDs in EU countries: an application on needs and gaps for CVD risk stratification in diabetes; d) Use of federated software to measure the impact of risk factors and data quality for cardiovascular risk prediction among people with diabetes, using cohorts extracted from federated diabetes registers in Europe; e) Use of federated analytics to monitor the impact of risk factors in NCDs: an application comparing the accuracy of different CVD prediction models in diabetes;

- “knowledge to practice”, i.e. how indicators are used by policy makers, doctors and patients to improve outcomes: Data linkage and interoperability. Privacy, data governance and ethics in the handling of sensitive data: assessment of current practices in the field of diabetes. An additional report on the engagement of stakeholders is expected to be delivered in the fall of year 2025.

The deliverables have been finalised to ensure that indicators considered by CHIEF are not only evidence-based and policy oriented but are also feasible and achievable through small pilot projects that can be used as a proof of concept of the functionality of the framework.

Conclusions

CHIEF seeks to provide a sustainable and practical solution to a periodic collection in the EU of NCD indicators that has so far proved elusive. The initiative considers all the elements that have proved challenging to overcome in a series of EU projects carried out during the last two decades under the banner of health information.

Recognising the inherent complexities, CHIEF keeps the focus at the broader generic level of NCDs, rather than focusing on specific challenges within any one disease domain. In its initial specifications, diabetes has been taken only as an exemplary case of more complex situations, applicable to all chronic diseases and multimorbid conditions.

The initiative is now entering its second phase, in which experts and partner organisations will collate data from a core set of data sources and registries from different parts of Europe to demonstrate how the federated platform can calculate a basic set of NCD indicators within a cohesive framework. Using the results of the first phase, a pilot study has been designed to show how indicators can be fully contextualised within their relative data sources, proposing a reference model that can be useful for implementation within EHDS (20).

The second phase of CHIEF will close at the end of year 2026, when a final report will discuss the main results obtained, outlining the key recommendations for the following steps of the European Commission, towards the regular publication of NCD indicators.

These results will help predefine the elements needed by the EHDS to operate a system of unbiased indicators, considering all the relevant functions activated in a federated system of data catalogues that will require searchable metadata descriptions of individual data sets.

In this context, the collaborative experience of registry networks may provide unique insight into the clinical content and epidemiological interpretation of health information accessible to the EHDS.

In consequence, CHIEF and the EHDS are complementary to each other and will together provide the synergies for defining and exploiting data sets for meaningful comparison across the EU.

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Author contributions

All authors provided a substantial contribution to the production of the manuscript. FC conceived and drafted the paper. NN revised the paper and ensured the correspondence of the contents with the objectives and tasks included in the collaboration.

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